

Vertical thickening versus lateral extrusion during India-Asia continental collision: 3-D thermo-mechanical modeling

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1. Datasets of all the models as summarized in Table1.

Model-1.zip

Model-2.zip

Model-3.zip

Model-4.zip

Model-5.zip

Model-6.zip

Model-7.zip

Model-8.zip

Model-9.zip

Model-10.zip

Model-11.zip

Model-12.zip

Model-13.zip

Model-14.zip

Model-15.zip

Model-16.zip

Model-17.zip

Model-18.zip

Model-19.zip

Model-20.zip

2. Datasets of the topography and GPS velocity field in Figure1.

Topography and GPS.zip